

SPEECH ERRORS AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM
TERMIZ DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI TALABASI
ALLANAZAROVA RUXSHONA BAHODIR QIZI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari yo'l qo'yishi mumkin bo'lgan lug'aviy-uslubiy, morfologik-uslubiy, sintaktik-uslubiy xatolar to'g'risida va ularni bartaraf qilish haqida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Lug'aviy-uslubiy, morfologik-uslubiy, sintaktik-uslubiy.

Abstract: This article describes the lexical-methodical, morphological-methodical, syntactic-methodical errors that elementary school students can make and how to eliminate them.

Key words: Lexical-stylistic, morphological-stylistic, syntactic-stylistic.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны лексико-методические, морфолого-методические, синтаксико-методические ошибки, которые могут совершать учащиеся начальной школы, и способы их устранения.

Ключевые слова: Лексико-стилистический, морфолого-стилистический, синтаксико-стилистический.

Speech errors include wrong (inappropriate) chosen words, wrongly structured sentences, wrong use of morphological forms. It is more difficult to work on such mistakes in elementary grades, because the short theoretical information given in the native language program is not enough to correct and prevent them.

It is necessary to know the main types of speech errors in order to carry out planned and regular work on improving children's speech. The study of such speech errors, as well as the examination of their causes, prepares the ground for correcting and preventing errors. Speech errors are divided into three types: lexical-stylistic, morphological-stylistic, syntactic-stylistic.

Vocabulary and stylistic errors are more common in elementary grades. Such errors include:

1. Using the same word over and over again. The reason for this error is, firstly, the student pays little attention to the use of the word and repeatedly uses the word in the active dictionary; secondly, the student's vocabulary is small, he does not know synonyms, he cannot use pronouns instead of repeated words. If the teacher explains well that in order not to use a word repeatedly, it is necessary to use its synonyms or pronouns instead of the same word, then a young student can read the text carefully and correct his repetitions relatively quickly.

2. Not being able to use the word in its exact sense as a result of not understanding the meaning or edge of the meaning. Such a mistake occurs because the child's speech is not well developed, and the vocabulary is small.

3. Use of dialectal words. Students use such words under the influence of their parents' speech and speech environment. Based on the formation of concepts used in the literary language, the skill of not using dialect-specific words is formed. Since lexical errors are different, the methods of correcting and explaining them are also different, but there is a common way to prevent such errors: to create a good speech environment, to analyze the text read and retold from a linguistic point of view, is to explain the meaning of the words in the text.

Morphological and stylistic errors include errors resulting from incorrect use of word form, word-changing and word-forming adverbs. Syntactic and stylistic errors include errors in word order and sentence structure. Such errors are very diverse. Compositional, logical, and argumentative misstatements are not grammatical errors. A typical compositional error includes the non-compliance of an essay, story, statement with a structured plan, that is, a violation of coherence in the presentation of events and observations. During the preparation of the essay, if the students do not have an orderly, unplanned work in observing, collecting material, selecting evidence, they cannot clearly visualize how to start the story, what to write about next, and how to end it, as a result, they make a compositional error. . Such a mistake is the result of not being able to fully grasp the content of the story, not being able to place the material in its place. The skill of writing a well-planned, coherent essay is a complex skill that students develop gradually through regular practice.

In conclusion, we can say that it is necessary to correct speech mistakes made by students in their oral and written speech in a timely manner. Let the student learn the correct version of the mistake he made, and if possible, understand the cause of the error. The most useful way to correct a mistake is for the student to correct the mistake he/she has made, and if the student cannot correct the mistake, the teacher will correct it. . It is corrected depending on the type of error: we can express our opinion that the sentence or phrase is restructured, the word is replaced by another, the necessary word is added, the excess is crossed out.

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